

185-OR: The Role of Optical Coherent Tomography in the Estimation of Cardiovascular Risk in Asymptomatic Patients with Type 1 Diabetes

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Introduction & Objective: Data on cardiovascular (CV) risk in patients with type 1 diabetes (T1D) is lacking. Our study aimed to assess coronary arteries in high-risk T1D patients using optical coherent tomography (OCT) to estimate their CV risk.

Methods: Sixty-two patients with T1D > 10 years, age 30-67 years, with no history of CVD were examined by carotid ultrasound and coronary artery calcium (CAC) score. Twelve patients were recognized as high-risk defined as CAC score >400 and/or presence of ≥ 2 carotid plaques. Patients were subsequently examined by coronary angiography and OCT.

Results: Mean age was 64.5 ± 1.8 years, T1D duration 36 ± 11.5 years, HbA1c 7.5 ± 0.8 % and baseline LDL 88.9 ± 21.3 mg/dl. Thin-cap fibroatheroma (TCFA [Figure-A]) was identified in 7/12 (58.3%) patients and very high-risk plaque (TCFA with lumen area < 3.5 mm² [B], lipid arch $> 180^\circ$ and macrophages [C]) was present in 4/12 (33.3%) patients. We saw intraluminal thrombus [D] and cholesterol crystal [E] in 3/12 (25%) patients. A strong correlation between OCT stenosis and CAC score at the left anterior descending artery (Pearson's $r=0.75$, $p=0.005$) was identified.

Conclusion: Our study showed that asymptomatic T1D patients with high CAC score and carotid plaques had very severe OCT findings. We observed a significant proportion of high-risk lesions potentially associated with plaque rupture and risk of CV death.

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Disclosure

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